

On the Nature of Magnetism

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Abstract

This paper introduces a new paradigm for understanding magnetism as the **curvature** of the electric field emitted by a moving charge. I first demonstrate how the uniform motion of a point charge induces a **rotation** of the electric field line at every point in space surrounding its trajectory. This rotation systematically curves the electric field line in a way that can be mathematically quantified. By incorporating this curvature into a modified form of the Biot-Savart law (for a moving point charge), I derive an equation that reveals magnetism to fundamentally be a product of charge and electric field curvature.

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1 Introduction

Where does the magnetic field come from? The science of physics informs us that a moving charge induces a magnetic field in all points of space surrounding its line of motion. But why? What is it specifically about this union of charge and motion that conjures up some mysterious magnetic manifestation?

The current scientific consensus seems to view magnetism as a relativistic aspect of electricity [PM13, p. 237]. I believe this to be a true but incomplete description of magnetism for the following reasons:

1. Current theories describe the impact of relativistic length contraction on the charge density of electrons moving down a wire [PM13, p. 259, §5.9]. I have no particular interest, however, in current-carrying wires. Rather, I seek to understand the fundamentals: why & how magnetism emerges from the motion of a single solitary charge moving in free space.
2. Relativistic length contraction is invoked to describe how a change in the charge density of a current-carrying wire leads to a test charge being either attracted to or repelled by the wire. As this explanation seems to suggest a straight line of force between the charge and wire, I fail to understand how this explains the *curved* trajectories we typically observe when charged particles move through magnetic fields.

I therefore set out to try and answer the basic question: Why and how does charge + motion = magnetism? This paper is a presentation of my findings.

2 Observations on a moving point charge

Let us represent a charged particle as a point in space from which electric lines of force (field lines) flow outwards in every possible direction [PM13, Fig. 1.9, p. 18], [YF18, Fig 21.18, p. 692] [WHR14, Fig. 22-6, p. 633]:

Figure 1: My schematic representation of a charged particle—or point charge.

Let us now choose an arbitrary point (which I will label **O** for **O**bservation point) from which we shall **o**bserve the effect of the moving charge. As all points surrounding a moving charge are known to systematically experience a disturbance of their magnetic field (and that is precisely the subject of our study), any arbitrary point should suit our purpose. Since we chose point **O** to be near our charged particle, we can expect an electric field line to flow from the charge out to point **O**, as lines of force originate at the charge and flow out in a straight line towards every possible direction in the surrounding space:

Figure 2: Electric field line flows from charged particle out to observation point O .

Now, let us put the particle in motion and observe what happens. After a short little while (let us call this time t_1), our particle will have traveled some distance from its initial position. The particle's electric nature has not changed, however, so we should expect, as before, that an electric field line will continue to flow from our charged particle out to point O . At this point in time, however, the particle has *moved* relative to its initial location. The outgoing lines of force no longer originate from the same point in space as they did at t_0 . Consequently, the angle at which the incoming electric field line reaches point O has actually rotated counterclockwise at time t_1 as compared to what was seen earlier at t_0 :

Figure 3: The left-to-right motion of the charged particle produces a counterclockwise rotation of the electric field line that reaches observation point O .

Notice that the angle of the electric field line arriving at point O is entirely determined by the particle's location along its line of motion. Since this relative position is continually changing as a consequence of the particle's velocity, so is the angle of the electric line of force that reaches point O . This field line will therefore continue its counterclockwise rotation around this point so long as the charge maintains its uniform linear motion.

Figure 4: Ongoing uniform motion of point charge correlates with ongoing rotation of electric field line that reaches observation point O .

Of course, point O was arbitrarily chosen. The same line of reasoning can be applied to any other arbitrarily chosen point around a moving charge (except those points collinear with the velocity vector):

Figure 5: Every point around a moving charge will be subject to a continuous rotation of the electric field line, so long as the source charge remains in motion.

We've just shown that a moving electric charge will induce a rotation of the electric field line at every point in the space that surrounds it. No moving charge, no rotating field line.

We also know from previous experiments and observations that a moving charge will induce a magnetic field at every point in space that surrounds its line of motion. No moving charge, no magnetic field.

This would seem to suggest that the magnetic field at a given point in spacetime might fundamentally be related to the rotational movement of the electric field line at that point.

3 Rotating electric field lines and curvature

What impact should we expect from such a dynamic on the electric field? In my quest to find out, I wrote a small JavaScript program that simulates a moving point charge that directs one unique field line towards some arbitrary stationary point in space. The source code is provided in Appendix A.

This next diagram shows the charged particle and observation point \mathbf{O} at the start of our experiment, before the charge is set in motion. We can see the electric field line emanated by the stationary charge passing through the observation point in a straight line.

Figure 6: Point charge emanates electric field line that reaches point \mathbf{O} and beyond.

In the following couple of diagrams, we observe what happens after the charge has been set in motion. Whereas the field lines of a stationary charge flow outwards in a straight line (Figure 6), we can see in the next illustrations that the charge's continuous motion results in an increasing curvature of the field line that continues to flow towards point \mathbf{O} .

Figure 7: Snapshots, at times t_1 and t_2 , of the same electric field line that continues to emanate from the charge (that is now in motion) towards observation point \mathbf{O} .

This is to be expected due to the continuity of electric fields [PM13, p. 18]. The line segment that flows through point \mathbf{O} at a certain moment in time

must remain connected to other segments of the field line that passed through the same observation point just a moment earlier, and also those that will get there a moment later—all coming from slightly different directions, since all are emanating from the same moving charge.

We observe an increasing curvature in the path of the field line as the charge continues on its course, and the angle between it and observation point \mathbf{O} continues to widen, as compared to its initial angle at t_0 .

Figure 8: Snapshots, at times t_3 and t_4 , of the very same electric field line that continues to flow from the moving point charge.

Notice how every radiated field point continues to radiate in a straight line away from its initial location and direction, as indicated by the dotted straight lines in both diagrams of figure 8. Not to be confused:

- *The direction of propagation* is the direction at which the field point propagates away from its initial location at the speed of light. This direction is determined at the moment of emission and is immutable.
- *The direction of the electric field line*, however, will typically evolve over time. It will follow the direction of propagation for *static electric fields* only. If the source charge is moving, this similarity no longer holds, and the directions *will be different* (as we've seen in the previous diagrams). In fact, an electromagnetic wave emitted by an accelerated charge will typically propagate almost perpendicularly to the direction of its electric vector (see [Zan12, p. 876, Fig. 23.2], [PM13, p. 253, Fig. 5.18 & 5.19]).

What this set of diagrams illustrates is that an electric field line emitted by a moving charge will follow a curved path through space. Figures 7 and 8 show this curvature at observation point \mathbf{O} , but we should understand that similar curvature happens *at every point in space* all around the moving charge.

With that in mind, how should we expect a free-moving charge to be affected by a curved electric field? We do know that a charged particle placed in an electric field feels a force in the same direction as (or opposite from, depending

This type of motion possesses angular velocity, which is a measure of the rotation rate (angular displacement) over time ($\omega = \frac{\Delta\theta}{\Delta t}$) [YF18, p. 273]. Angular velocity also has a vector form, $\vec{\omega}$, which points along the axis of rotation and has a magnitude equal to that of its angular speed [Mor07, p. 372-373].

Figure 10: Angular velocity

Note how this angular velocity vector is *also* parallel to the magnetic vector by transitivity, since both vectors are parallel to the axis of rotation. It is no mere coincidence that the magnetic vector should be so tightly coupled to these other two, as it is precisely the *rotation* of an electric field line around such an axis that is the cause of its curvature. This seems obvious from looking at the illustrations of section 3, but let us now show how to mathematically derive this curvature as a function of the field line's angular velocity.

3.2 Electric curvature

The formula we need to derive should yield the length of the radius that points from the polar origin to the field line's location at angle θ . We choose the pole to coincide with our point of rotation, and the polar axis to be tangent to the curved field line at that point:

Figure 11: Measuring the distance of a curved electric field line from the polar origin.

The electric field point that reaches location (r, θ) got there by crossing the pole at some point in the past, when its direction of propagation was θ radians from the polar axis. How long ago was that? $\omega = \frac{\theta}{t} \implies t = \frac{\theta}{\omega}$.

Knowing that the field propagates at the speed of light [FLS64a] c , we can calculate the magnitude of radius r for a given angle θ and rotation speed ω :

$$\|r\| = r(\theta, \omega) = \|\vec{v}\| \cdot t = c \cdot \frac{\theta}{\omega} \quad (1)$$

Since we will need to differentiate with respect to θ , and since the angular velocity ω represents a constant in that context, let us rewrite for convenience:

$$r(\theta, \omega) = \frac{c}{\omega} \cdot \theta \quad (2)$$

We can calculate the curvature of a function specified in polar coordinates[Wei]:

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{R} = \frac{|r^2 + 2r'^2 - rr''|}{(r^2 + r'^2)^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

Let us write down the various terms of this equation, as derived from 2:

- $r = r(\theta, \omega) = \frac{c}{\omega} \cdot \theta$
- $r' = \frac{dr}{d\theta} = \frac{c}{\omega}$
- $r'' = \frac{dr'}{d\theta} = 0$
- $r^2 = \frac{c^2}{\omega^2} \cdot \theta^2$
- $r'^2 = \frac{c^2}{\omega^2}$

Substituting each term of equation 3 by its value, we obtain the following curvature κ_e for the electric field line located at an angle of θ off the polar axis:

$$\kappa_e = \frac{|\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} \cdot \theta^2 + 2\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} - \frac{c}{\omega} \cdot 0|}{(\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} \cdot \theta^2 + \frac{c^2}{\omega^2})^{3/2}} \quad (4)$$

The specific value we seek is the curvature at the pole. At that location, the curve's tangent is parallel to the polar axis; the value of θ is therefore zero:

$$\kappa_e = \frac{|\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} \cdot 0^2 + 2\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} - \frac{c}{\omega} \cdot 0|}{(\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} \cdot 0^2 + \frac{c^2}{\omega^2})^{3/2}} = \frac{2\frac{c^2}{\omega^2}}{(\frac{c^2}{\omega^2})^{3/2}} = \frac{2}{(\frac{c^2}{\omega^2})^{1/2}} = \frac{2 \cdot \omega}{c} \quad (5)$$

That is the curvature of an electric field line at an arbitrary point around which it is spinning with angular velocity ω .

4 The fundamental nature of magnetism

The Biot-Savart law is an equation describing the magnetic field generated by a constant electric current. A modified version of this equation is commonly used to describe the magnetic field produced by a moving point charge¹ [YF18, p. 919, (28.2)]:

$$\vec{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot q \cdot \frac{\vec{v} \times \hat{r}}{\|\vec{r}\|^2} \quad (6)$$

Where:

- \vec{B} is the magnetic flux density (in teslas)
- μ_0 is the magnetic constant ($1.25663706 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m kg s}^{-2} \text{ A}^{-2}$)
- q represents the value of the charge (in Coulombs)
- \vec{v} is the velocity of the charge (in meters per second)
- \vec{r} the vector pointing from the charge out to observation point \mathbf{O}
- \hat{r} is the unit vector that is collinear with \vec{r}

Figure 12: The parameters that feed into the modified Biot-Savart equation.

This equation produces a vector that is the result of a cross product. The magnitude of this vector can be expressed as follows:

$$\|\vec{B}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot |q| \cdot \frac{\|\vec{v} \times \hat{r}\|}{\|\vec{r}\|^2} \quad (7)$$

Let us replace the magnitude of the cross product $\|\vec{v} \times \hat{r}\|$ by its value:

$$\|\vec{B}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot |q| \cdot \frac{\|\vec{v}\| \cdot \|\hat{r}\| \sin \theta}{\|\vec{r}\|^2} \quad (8)$$

¹Note that this equation is only applicable when $\vec{v} \ll c$

Which can be simplified, knowing $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ to be a unit vector:

$$\|\vec{\mathbf{B}}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot |q| \cdot \frac{\|\vec{\mathbf{v}}\| \sin \theta}{\|\vec{\mathbf{r}}\|^2} \quad (9)$$

Here, θ is the angle between vectors $\vec{\mathbf{v}}$ and $\vec{\mathbf{r}}$. If we decompose $\vec{\mathbf{v}}$ into two orthogonal components $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_1$ and $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2$, with $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_1$ chosen to be collinear with vector $\vec{\mathbf{r}}$, we obtain the following:

Figure 13: Orthogonal vectors $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_1$ (collinear with $\vec{\mathbf{r}}$) and $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2$ add up to $\vec{\mathbf{v}}$.

By definition,

$$\sin \theta = \frac{\|\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2\|}{\|\vec{\mathbf{v}}\|}$$

thus

$$\|\vec{\mathbf{v}}\| \sin \theta = \|\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2\|$$

This equality enables us to substitute $\|\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2\|$ into equation (9):

$$\|\vec{\mathbf{B}}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot |q| \cdot \frac{\|\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2\|}{\|\vec{\mathbf{r}}\|^2} \quad (10)$$

Let us remember that $\vec{\mathbf{v}}$ is the velocity of charge \mathbf{q} as it moves in the vicinity of observation point \mathbf{O} . The charge's motion, as we saw earlier, impels a rotation of the electric field line around point \mathbf{O} . The velocity of this rotation will thus be determined by the velocity $\vec{\mathbf{v}}$ of the moving charge, and hence by the two component vectors $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_1$ and $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2$.

Now, vector $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_1$ provides no rotational movement whatsoever to the field line, as it is collinear with $\vec{\mathbf{r}}$. No matter the magnitude of the $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_1$ component, it will always have zero impact on the rotational velocity of the collinear field line.

Vector $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2$, on the other hand, does have a role to play in the rotational velocity of the electric field line at point \mathbf{O} . In fact, being perpendicular to $\vec{\mathbf{r}}$, vector $\vec{\mathbf{v}}_2$ can appropriately be referred to as the field line's *linear velocity* at

the charge's location with respect to the field line's rotation around point \mathbf{O} . We can use this information to find the field's *angular* velocity ω at point \mathbf{O} : [Mor07, p. 373, (9.1)]

$$\omega = \frac{\text{linear velocity}}{\text{radius}} = \frac{\|\vec{v}_2\|}{\|\vec{r}\|}$$

This last equality enables us to rewrite equation 10, swapping in the angular velocity ω of the rotating electric field line:

$$\|\vec{B}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot |q| \cdot \frac{|\omega|}{\|\vec{r}\|}$$

or

$$\|\vec{B}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi r} \cdot |q \cdot \omega| \quad (11)$$

We can now make use of equation 5 to replace the newly added angular velocity term by its curvature-bearing equivalent:

$$\|\vec{B}\| = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi r} \cdot |q \cdot \frac{c \cdot \kappa_e}{2}| \quad (12)$$

Equation 12 may be further refined if we choose to make use of the known identity $c^2 = \frac{1}{\mu_0 \epsilon_0}$ [PM13, p. 281 (6.8)]. This enables us to swap out the magnetic constant μ_0 , and replace it by its equivalent $\frac{1}{c^2 \epsilon_0}$; which has the benefit of elegantly grouping all of the remaining constants together in the denominator:

$$\|\vec{B}\| = \frac{|q \cdot \kappa_e|}{c \epsilon_0 8\pi r} \quad (13)$$

This equation we've just derived from Biot-Savart describes the *magnitude* of the magnetic vector as a product of charge and curvature of the electric field. Alas, our vector has been downgraded to a mere scalar in the process. We can rectify this by introducing a binormal unit vector, which happens to be parallel to the axis of rotation at that location; i.e., as we've seen in section 3.1, parallel to the magnetic vector.

$$\vec{B}_m = \frac{-q \cdot |\kappa_e|}{c \epsilon_0 8\pi r} \cdot \vec{B}_i \quad (14)$$

where \vec{B}_m represents, of course, the *magnetic* vector and \vec{B}_i is the *binormal* unit vector of the curved electric field line (see Fig. 14). Notice how it became necessary to find a way to distinguish between the two \vec{B} vectors in this last equation. \vec{B}_m defined in terms of \vec{B}_i . How *cool* of a coincidence is that?

Although the sign (direction) of the binormal vector \vec{B}_i is unaffected by the polarity of the moving charge (only by the charge's velocity vector), that is not the case for the magnetic field, which *is* affected by the charge's polarity (see Fig. 14 below). The minus sign in front of charge q in equation 14 is there to provide the necessary adjustment to account for that fact:

- Vectors \vec{B}_m and \vec{B}_i only point in the same direction when the moving charge is negative (Fig. 14a). When that is the case, the expression $-q$ becomes positive (negative of a negative), leaving intact the sign of the expression as a whole, thus returning a magnetic vector \vec{B}_m that points in the same direction as the binormal unit vector \vec{B}_i .
- In the case of a *positive* charge, however, vectors \vec{B}_m and \vec{B}_i will point in diametrically opposite directions (Fig. 14b). In that situation, $-q$ causes the whole expression to become negative, thereby *reversing* the sign of the binormal unit vector \vec{B}_i . This results in a magnetic vector \vec{B}_m that points in the opposite direction—precisely what is required in this context.

Figure 14: The magnetic and binormal vectors at a given point along a curved electric field line will either point in the same direction or in diametrically opposed directions—depending on the polarity of the source charge.

What has been achieved with equation 14 is what I would call a *descriptive* mathematical formulation for the magnetic field derived from the *prescriptive* Biot-Savart modified equation 6.

I consider Biot-Savart to be *prescriptive* because, in my view, it represents a useful recipe to obtain the magnetic field in a given context. You plug in your various parameters, and voilà! Out comes a magnetic vector. The *meaning* of this equation and of its unseemly cross product, however, is not very intuitive.

Equation 14, in contrast, *describes* the magnetic field in a way that expresses its fundamental nature: a function of charge and curvature of the electric field (i.e., "a moving charge").

5 Supporting arguments

In this section we will examine several properties associated with magnetism that are well known, but perhaps a bit of a challenge to intuitively understand in the context of our current state of knowledge on the subject. We will show how this paper's innovative interpretation of magnetism can help provide simple, clear and coherent explanations of these phenomena.

5.1 The shape of the magnetic field

The Danish physicist Hans Christian Ørsted discovered in 1820 that a magnetic field always encircles a current-carrying wire, and that the field lines lie in a plane that is perpendicular to the wire [Fah84, p. 274]:

Figure 15: **Magnetic field lines** induced by an **electric current**.

We have shown in section 3.1 how at every point surrounding a moving charge there will be a magnetic vector perpendicular to the plane of rotation of the electric field line. Recall that this plane of rotation *includes* the charge's line of motion. This implies that the magnetic vector will also, necessarily, be perpendicular to *the charge's line of motion*. In other words, always *perpendicular to a current-carrying wire*.

5.2 The orthogonality of electric and magnetic vectors

Why are the electric and magnetic vectors emanating from a given source almost always perpendicular to one another[FLS64b]? We've seen in section 3.1 how the electric field lines lie within a plane of rotation that is perpendicular to the magnetic vector. Which explains the relative orientation between these vectors.

5.3 The polarity of the magnetic force

The magnetic force acting on a charged particle can be calculated using the Lorentz force law[Gri13, p. 212, (5.1)]. You'll notice that the sign of this force depends on the polarity of the moving charge. Why is that?

$$\vec{F} = q(\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \quad (15)$$

The reason becomes obvious when you realize that what we call the magnetic force is actually the result of a moving charge being affected by a curved electric field. As we already know, two electric charges will react differently to the presence of an electric field if they have different polarities. A positive test charge will be accelerated in the direction of the electric field, whereas a negative charge will feel an equivalent force, but in the opposite direction[YF18, p. 691].

This explains why the same magnetic field will make a point charge curve in one direction or the other, depending on the charge's polarity. All charges will be guided by the same curved electric field. However, the very same clockwise curve seen from one direction will be transformed into a counterclockwise curve if you reverse the polarity—and therefore, also, the direction of traversal:

Figure 16: Positive and negative charges reacting differently to a curved electric field.

5.4 The magnetic force only affects moving charges

As we have argued in section 3, magnetism's effect is fundamentally linked to the continuous rotation of the electric field line that acts on a charged particle as it travels through a curved electric field. It manifests itself as a *change of direction*. Often described as *perpendicular to the velocity vector*.

If there is no motion, there is no direction to be changed. If there is no velocity vector, a perpendicular force makes no sense. The magnetic force is undetectable in static charges very simply because the property that is affected by the magnetic force (the velocity vector) is simply absent in *static* charges.

5.5 The magnetic force vector is a cross product

If we consider the *magnitude* of the magnetic force, we notice that it depends on the angle that the velocity vector \vec{v} makes relative to the magnetic field \vec{B} :

$$\|\vec{F}\| = \|q(\vec{v} \times \vec{B})\| = q\|\vec{v}\| \cdot \|\vec{B}\| \cdot \sin \theta \quad (16)$$

A question that naturally comes to mind is: why the need for a $\sin \theta$ multiplier when calculating the force's magnitude?

The short answer is that the magnetic force is the result of a cross product of vectors, and that is how one calculates the magnitude of a cross product. But that misses the point. Why the need for a cross product to begin with?

As we've seen in section 3, it is the movement of the charged particle *through the curved electric field* that is responsible for the dynamic rotation of the field line felt by the particle and therefore also responsible for its curved trajectory. It is important to note that these distances and velocities are to be considered in relation to the *plane of rotation*, which is the dimension in which the electric field is actually curving. If there is no velocity *in that plane*, then the charged particle remains unaffected by the curvature, though it may still be in motion; for example, if it were moving perpendicular to the plane of rotation.

That situation is, in fact, well known. We were all taught in physics class that a charged particle moving parallel to the magnetic field (i.e., perpendicular to the plane of rotation) is unaffected by the magnetic force (see equation 17):

Figure 17: A charged particle moving through a magnetic field in a direction parallel to the magnetic field lines remains unaffected by the field, and feels no magnetic force.

That is because the particle's XY coordinates *in the plane of rotation* are constant. The charge does not move *in that plane* and therefore never gets to other regions of the plane where changes in the direction of the curving electric field could potentially impact the particle's trajectory. There may be motion, but only in a direction that is orthogonal to the plane of rotation; a direction where there is *no* electric field curvature.

That is, of course, consistent with Lorentz's equation for the magnetic force. Since the angle θ between the charge's velocity vector and the magnetic field lines is zero (they are parallel), the magnetic force will also necessarily be zero:

$$\|\vec{F}\| = q\|\vec{v}\| \cdot \|\vec{B}\| \sin \theta = q\|\vec{v}\| \cdot \|\vec{B}\| \cdot \sin 0 = q\|\vec{v}\| \cdot \|\vec{B}\| \cdot 0 = 0 \quad (17)$$

In the more general case, the charged particle moves through the magnetic field at an angle θ and speed determined by its velocity vector \vec{v} :

Figure 18: A charged particle moving through a magnetic field at velocity \vec{v} and at angle θ relative to the direction of the magnetic field lines.

As we've just seen, however, it is the relative speed *in the plane of rotation* that contributes to the magnetic curving effect. Velocity vector \vec{v} can be decomposed into its 2 orthogonal constituent vectors \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 , parallel to the plane of rotation and the magnetic field line respectively.

Notice that vector \vec{v}_2 is parallel to the magnetic field, and is therefore unaffected by the curving electric field lines. Vector \vec{v}_1 , however (the projection of \vec{v} onto the rotation plane), does have an impact on the charge's curving trajectory, as it represents the relative velocity of \vec{v} *in the rotation plane*.

It is thus this vector, \vec{v}_1 , that represents the relative speed which needs to be taken into account by the Lorentz equation. We know that by definition:

$$\frac{\|\vec{v}_1\|}{\|\vec{v}\|} = \sin \theta$$

Therefore,

$$\|\vec{v}_1\| = \|\vec{v}\| \cdot \sin \theta$$

Which explains the presence of the $\sin\theta$ multiplier in the Lorentz equation. It represents the adjustment factor that must be applied to the magnitude of the particle's velocity vector \vec{v} in order to obtain its correct velocity in the planar frame of reference where the electric field lines are actually curving.

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A Appendix: Javascript code used for illustrating section 3

Simulation of a moving point charge that fires one isolated field line towards the same stationary target point in space – all the while moving along in a uniform manner with respect to its target.

Note that the javascript code below is embedded within an HTML document that can be loaded into a web browser to visualize the selected field line(s).

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>

  <head>
    <title>
      Simulating the electric field line of a moving point charge
    </title>
    <script>
//
// some useful mathematical concepts & functions
//

// a 2D point with x & y coordinates
class Point {
  constructor(x, y) {
    this.x = x;
    this.y = y;
  }
}

// returns x-component of a line segment having specified length & angle
function deltaX(angle, length) {
  let radians = Math.radians(angle);
  return length * Math.cos(radians);
}

// returns y-component of a line segment having specified length & angle
function deltaY(angle, length) {
  let radians = Math.radians(angle);
  return length * Math.sin(radians);
}

// returns the distance between 2 points
function distance(pt1, pt2) {
  return Math.sqrt((pt2.x - pt1.x)**2 + (pt2.y - pt1.y)**2);
}

// returns the angle between 2 points (in degrees)
function angleOf(pt1, pt2) {
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    let deltaX = pt2.x - pt1.x;
    let hypotenuse = distance(pt1, pt2);

    return Math.degrees(Math.acos(deltaX/hypotenuse));
}

// returns point that is length distance from origin at specified angle
function getTargetPoint(origin, angle, length) {
    return new Point(
        origin.x + deltaX(angle, length),
        origin.y + deltaY(angle, length)
    );
}

// Convert from degrees to radians.
Math.radians = function(degrees) {
    return degrees * Math.PI / 180;
}

// Convert from radians to degrees.
Math.degrees = function(radians) {
    return radians * 180 / Math.PI;
}

//
// the Model
//

// point in space towards which every radiated field point
// is to be aimed at the moment of its creation
let targetPoint = new Point(150, 150);

// speed of field point propagation in pixels per increment
// this value was chosen to optimize visual proportions for clarity
let pixelsPerIncrement = 4;

// a field line is made up of FieldPoints
class FieldPoint {

    constructor(origin, direction) {
        // location of this field point
        this.location = new Point(origin.x, origin.y);

        // its direction (angle of propagation)
        this.direction = direction;
    }

    radiate() {
        // advance pixelsPerIncrement units along its angle of propagation
        this.location = getTargetPoint(

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        this.location,
        this.direction,
        pixelsPerIncrement
    );
}
} // FieldPoint

class ChargedParticle {

    constructor(location) {
        // current location of this charged particle
        this.location = new Point(location.x, location.y);

        // array of field points which collectively make up the field line
        this.fieldLine = [];
        this.fieldPointCount = 0;
    }

    radiate() {
        // add new FieldPoint to fieldLine
        this.fieldLine[this.fieldPointCount++] = new FieldPoint(
            this.location,
            angleOf(this.location, targetPoint)
        );

        for(let i = 0; i < this.fieldPointCount; i++) {
            // advance each fieldPoint that is part of fieldLine
            this.fieldLine[i].radiate();
        }
    }

    // utility method to provision initial collection of fieldPoints
    // simulating a field line prior to the motion of charged particle
    radiateMultiple(count) {
        for (let i = 0; i < count; i++) {
            // create new fieldPoint, advance them all an increment
            this.radiate();
        }
    }

    drawFieldLine(ctx) {
        // line to draw starts at current charge location
        let ptFrom = this.location;

        // we need to traverse the array in reverse order since
        // it is ordered from older field points to newer ones
        // and field line is to be drawn from its source outwards
        for (let i = this.fieldPointCount-1; i >= 0; i--) {

            let currentPoint = this.fieldLine[i];

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        drawLine(ctx, ptFrom, currentPoint.location, red);

        // prepare for next iteration (and new line segment)
        ptFrom = currentPoint.location;
    }
} // ChargedParticle

//
// display functions
//

let red = "rgb(255, 0, 0)";
let grey = "rgb(200, 200, 200)";

function drawLine(ctx, ptFrom, ptTo, strokeStyle) {
    ctx.beginPath();

    ctx.strokeStyle = strokeStyle;
    ctx.moveTo(ptFrom.x, ptFrom.y);
    ctx.lineTo(ptTo.x, ptTo.y);

    ctx.stroke();
}

// create & return canvas context to be used for drawing
function getContext(id) {
    let canvas = document.getElementById(id);
    if (canvas.getContext) {
        // initialise 2D context
        const ctx = canvas.getContext("2d");
        ctx.lineWidth = 2;

        return ctx;
    }
    return null;
}

//
// display the graph
//

function showGraph() {

    // get drawing context of canvas present in document body
    let ctx = getContext("canvas");
    if (ctx != null) {

        // y-coordinate of point charge horizontal trajectory
        let chargeHeight = 50;

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// start & end points of the traveling point charge
let ptStart = new Point(50, chargeHeight);
let ptEnd = new Point(250, chargeHeight);

// create new charged particle at location ptStart
let charge = new ChargedParticle(ptStart);

// radiate a bit (statically) before setting charge in motion
charge.radiateMultiple(150);

// draw straight grey lines towards targetPoint
// coming from charge's location at t0, t1, t2, t3 & t4
drawLine(ctx, new Point(50, 50), targetPoint, grey);
drawLine(ctx, new Point(100, 50), targetPoint, grey);
drawLine(ctx, new Point(150, 50), targetPoint, grey);
drawLine(ctx, new Point(200, 50), targetPoint, grey);
drawLine(ctx, new Point(250, 50), targetPoint, grey);

// field line(s) to be drawn when charge is at these x-locations
let snapshots = [150]; // 50, 100, 150, 200, 250];

// move charged particle from ptStart to ptEnd
for (let posX = ptStart.x; posX <= ptEnd.x; posX++) {
  // horizontally position charge at current increment
  charge.location.x = posX;

  // periodically draw field line at predefined snapshot values
  if (snapshots.includes(posX)) {
    charge.drawFieldLine(ctx);
  }

  // radiate field line outward
  charge.radiate();
}
}

// call showGraph() after document is loaded
window.addEventListener("load", showGraph);

</script>
</head>
<body>
  <div>
    <canvas id="canvas" width="1000" height="1000">
    </canvas>
  </div>
</body>
</html>

```